

Supplementary Materials

Longitudinal Self-Monitoring of Physical Condition Under Continued Self-Care: A Single Case Report

Takahashi. M

Independent researcher

Correspondence: takahashi.m.contact@gmail.com

Overview

These supplementary materials provide detailed methodological descriptions and extended statistical analyses that complement the results presented in the main manuscript. Specifically, correlations among the collected variables are shown in a 10×10 correlation matrix, and the distributions of tympanic temperatures and each symptom score by time of day are visualized using box-and-whisker plots. In addition, the results of multiple regression analyses examining changes in body temperature before and after bathing are also presented. These materials provide a detailed view of the underlying data structure and the relationships among variables, which are simplified in the main text.

Study 1. Correlation Between Indicators

Methods

For descriptive purposes, a 10×10 correlation matrix was constructed based on Pearson's correlation coefficients for the following 10 variables: left tympanic temperature, right tympanic temperature, bilateral mean tympanic temperature, axillary body temperature, subjective head heat sensation score, pain score, fatigue score, sternocleidomastoid tension score, subjective psychological distress score, and lemborexant dose. Pairwise correlation coefficients (r), 95% confidence intervals, q -values, and degrees of freedom were calculated.

Multiple testing correction was performed using the Benjamini–Hochberg method, and q-values were calculated. However, these statistical values are presented solely as descriptive information and were not used for hypothesis testing.

For the analysis of tympanic temperature, data from a certain period of approximately one week prior to probe cover replacement were excluded. Because strong structural correlations were expected among left, right, and bilateral mean tympanic temperatures, correlations among these variables were excluded from the primary interpretation of the matrix. Due to missing data, the number of valid data points used to calculate each correlation coefficient varied for each variable pair. Definitions and basic measurement methods for each variable are described in the Methods section of the main text.

Results

Correlation coefficients (r) for the 10×10 correlation matrix are presented in Supplementary Table S1, and 95% confidence intervals, p-values, q-values, and degrees of freedom (df) are presented in Supplementary Table S2.

Tympanic temperatures (left, right, and bilateral mean) showed positive correlations with subjective head heat sensation scores, as well as with pain and fatigue scores. Among the symptom scores, mutual positive correlations were observed between head heat sensation, pain, and fatigue. Lemborexant dose exhibited negative correlations with pain and fatigue scores. In contrast, associations between tympanic temperature and subjective psychological distress scores were weak. No consistent correlation patterns were observed among the other variables.

Supplementary Table S2. Pairwise correlations between measured variables and subjective symptom scores (r, 95% CI, q-value, df)

Variable 1	Variable 2	r	95% CI	q	df
Left tympanic temperature	Axillary Body Temperature	0.353	0.158 to 0.522	0.0013	88
Left tympanic temperature	Subjective Head Heat Sensation Score	0.652	0.588 to 0.708	1.764×10^{-42}	351
Left tympanic temperature	Pain Score	0.24	0.141 to 0.338	1.42×10^{-5}	351
Left tympanic temperature	Fatigue Score	0.348	0.253 to 0.436	9.24×10^{-11}	351
Left tympanic temperature	Sternocleidomastoid tension score	-0.014	-0.206 to 0.181	0.915	101
Left tympanic temperature	Subjective Psychological Distress Score	0.016	-0.178 to 0.209	0.915	101
Left tympanic temperature	Lemborexant dose	-0.059	-0.235 to 0.125	0.648	116
Right tympanic temperature	Axillary Body Temperature	0.309	0.109 to 0.485	0.005	88
Right tympanic temperature	Subjective Head Heat Sensation Score	0.439	0.351 to 0.520	3.89×10^{-17}	351
Right tympanic temperature	Pain Score	0.098	-0.006 to 0.201	0.105	351
Right tympanic temperature	Fatigue Score	0.164	0.060 to 0.263	0.004	351
Right tympanic temperature	Sternocleidomastoid tension score	-0.058	-0.249 to 0.137	0.653	101

Right tympanic temperature	Subjective Psychological Distress Score	-0.153	-0.337 to 0.0416	0.191	101
Right tympanic temperature	Lemborexant dose	0.022	-0.159 to 0.202	0.896	116
Bilateral mean tympanic temperature	Axillary Body Temperature	0.367	0.173 to 0.533	0.001	88
Bilateral mean tympanic temperature	Subjective Head Heat Sensation Score	0.591	0.518 to 0.655	1.39×10^{-33}	351
Bilateral mean tympanic temperature	Pain Score	0.177	0.074 to 0.276	0.002	351
Bilateral mean tympanic temperature	Fatigue Score	0.269	0.170 to 0.363	1.07×10^{-6}	351
Bilateral mean tympanic temperature	Sternocleidomastoid tension score	-0.051	-0.242 to 0.144	0.694	101
Bilateral mean tympanic temperature	Subjective Psychological Distress Score	-0.114	-0.301 to 0.081	0.350	101
Bilateral mean tympanic temperature	Lemborexant dose	-0.02	-0.200 to 0.162	0.896	116
Axillary Body Temperature	Subjective Head Heat Sensation Score	0.36	0.166 to 0.527	0.001	89
Axillary Body Temperature	Pain Score	0.086	-0.123 to 0.286	0.553	89
Axillary Body Temperature	Fatigue Score	0.131	-0.0772 to 0.328	0.3255	89

Axillary Body Temperature	Sternocleidomastoid tension score	0.209	-0.302 to 0.627	0.553	15
Axillary Body Temperature	Subjective Psychological Distress Score	-0.3	-0.682 to 0.211	0.350	15
Axillary Body Temperature	Lemborexant dose	0.577	0.284 to 0.746	0.001	35
Subjective Head Heat Sensation Score	Pain Score	0.404	0.318 to 0.483	3.15×10^{-16}	395
Subjective Head Heat Sensation Score	Fatigue Score	0.589	0.521 to 0.650	3.78×10^{-37}	395
Subjective Head Heat Sensation Score	Sternocleidomastoid tension score	0.284	0.125 to 0.429	0.001	139
Subjective Head Heat Sensation Score	Subjective Psychological Distress Score	0.455	0.313 to 0.577	6.91×10^{-8}	139
Subjective Head Heat Sensation Score	Lemborexant dose	-0.052	-0.221 to 0.120	0.648	130
Pain Score	Fatigue Score	0.581	0.512 to 0.643	4.13×10^{-36}	395
Pain Score	Sternocleidomastoid tension score	0.29	0.131 to 0.434	0.001	139

Pain Score	Subjective Psychological Distress Score	0.317	0.160 to 0.458	0.000	139
Pain Score	Lemborexant dose	-0.412	-0.544 to -0.259	1.42×10^{-5}	130
Fatigue Score	Sternocleidomastoid tension score	0.311	0.153 to 0.453	0.000	139
Fatigue Score	Subjective Psychological Distress Score	0.55	0.423 to 0.655	1.02×10^{-11}	139
Fatigue Score	Lemborexant dose	-0.181	-0.341 to -0.010	0.064	130
Sternocleidomastoid tension score	Subjective Psychological Distress Score	0.421	0.275 to 0.548	8.23×10^{-7}	139
Sternocleidomastoid tension score	Lemborexant dose	-0.1	-0.377 to 0.192	0.639	45
Subjective Psychological Distress Score	Lemborexant dose	0.013	-0.275 to 0.299	0.933	45

Study 2. Descriptive Analysis of Indicators Measured Three Times Daily (Morning, Noon, Nighth)

Methods

In this study, the following indicators, measured three times daily (morning, noon, nighth), were descriptively analyzed to examine differences in their distributions by time of day: left tympanic temperature, right tympanic temperature, bilateral mean tympanic temperature, axillary body temperature, subjective head heat sensation score, pain score, fatigue score, sternocleidomastoid tension score, and subjective psychological distress score.

For each indicator, box-and-whisker plots were generated for the morning, noon, and night measurements. This analysis was exploratory in nature and was not intended for statistical hypothesis testing.

Results

Box-and-whisker plots for each indicator by morning, noon, and night measurements are presented in Supplementary Figures S1–S8. The values shown in the plots represent the medians.

Supplementary Figure S1. Box-and-whisker plot of left tympanic temperature by morning, noon, and night measurements

Supplementary Figure S2. Box-and-whisker plot of right tympanic temperature by morning, noon, and night measurements

Supplementary Figure S3. Box-and-whisker plot of bilateral mean tympanic temperature by morning, noon, and night measurements

Supplementary Figure S4. Boxplot of Subjective Head Heat Sensation Scores by Morning, Noon, and Night

Supplementary Figure S5. Boxplot of Pain Scores by Morning, Noon, and Night

Supplementary Figure S6. Boxplot of Fatigue Scores by Morning, Noon, and Night

Supplementary Figure S7. Boxplot of Sternocleidomastoid tension scores by Morning, Noon, and Night

Supplementary Figure S8. Boxplot of Subjective Psychological Distress Scores by Morning, Noon, and Night

Study 3. Descriptive Analysis of Tympanic Temperature Changes (ΔT) Before and After Bathing

Methods

Tympanic temperatures of the left and right ears were measured using an ear thermometer immediately before and after bathing, and the modal values were recorded. Bathing was generally conducted in a bathtub at approximately 40° C for around 10 minutes, but the duration was adjusted according to the participant's comfort and physical condition.

The change in tympanic temperature before and after bathing (ΔT) was calculated by subtracting the pre-bath tympanic temperature from the post-bath tympanic temperature.

To explore potential associations after accounting for pre-bath tympanic temperature, multiple regression analyses were conducted with ΔT as the dependent variable. Pre-bath tympanic temperature was entered into all models as a covariate. Each of the following variables was then added individually to separate models: bilateral mean tympanic temperature, axillary body temperature, subjective head heat sensation score, pain score, fatigue score, sternocleidomastoid tension score, subjective psychological distress score, and lemborexant dose.

Results

The results of multiple regression analyses with ΔT as the dependent variable are presented in Supplementary Table S3. Within the exploratory scope of the analyses, none of the examined indicators showed a clear effect on ΔT .

Supplementary Table S3. Multiple regression analysis results for ΔT (change in tympanic temperature before and after bathing)

Independent variable	β (regression coefficient)	95% CI	p
Bilateral mean tympanic temperature	2.2	-2.44 to 6.83	0.35
Axillary body temperature	3.07	-4.29 to 10.44	0.40
Subjective head heat sensation score	0.23	-0.32 to 0.77	0.41
Pain score	0.057	-0.45 to 0.57	0.82
Fatigue score	0.23	-0.12 to 0.59	0.20
Sternocleidomastoid tension score	-0.02	-0.09 to 0.04	0.51
Subjective psychological distress score	0.004	-0.05 to 0.06	0.87
Lemborexant dose	0.45	-0.22 to 1.13	0.18